

CLIENT SATISFACTION UNVEILED: EVALUATING SERVICE QUALITY, EMPLOYEE COMPETENCE AND SUSTAINABLE ENVIRONMENTAL PRACTICES IN A NEGOSYO CENTER IN MISAMIS ORIENTAL

Romelyn M. Maulas, Cyril C. Chavez

Business Administration, Lourdes College Inc., Cagayan de Oro City, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

The Negosyo Center serves as a key government-led hub that supports local business development, making client satisfaction critical to its overall effectiveness. In response to the growing need for improved public service delivery and business support, this study evaluates the association between selected factors—service quality, employee competence, sustainable environmental practices, and client satisfaction among Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in a Negosyo Center in Misamis Oriental. Utilizing a descriptive-correlational research design, data were gathered from 104 MSME clients through a researcher-made questionnaire and random sampling. Descriptive statistics such as mean, frequency, percentage, and standard deviation were used to summarize responses. Findings showed that all three variables were rated “very high,” indicating strong agreement among clients on the presence and quality of these practices. Among the service quality dimensions, tangibility received the highest rating, followed by responsiveness, empathy, reliability, and assurance. For employee competence, professionalism ranked slightly higher than employee skills, while sustainable environmental practices were also seen as “always practiced.” Client satisfaction was likewise rated “very high.” Spearman’s rho correlation revealed that all three independent variables had a significant positive association with client satisfaction. Employee competence showed the strongest correlation, followed by service quality and sustainable environmental practices. However, awareness of sustainability practices and problem-solving skills were identified as areas needing improvement to sustain quality service delivery. The study concludes that strengthening employee competence, enhancing service quality, and increasing awareness of sustainability initiatives are essential to

further improving client satisfaction at the Negosyo Center. Future research may explore longitudinal assessments of service delivery outcomes, comparative evaluations across multiple Negosyo Centers nationwide, and the mediating roles of digital innovation and regulatory compliance in shaping sustainable client engagement.

Keywords: *service quality, employee competence, sustainable environmental practices, client satisfaction, Negosyo Center*

INTRODUCTION

While national policies such as the "Go Negosyo Act" (Republic Act No. 10644) and the "Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act" (Republic Act No. 11032) were enacted to strengthen MSME development and enhance public service delivery, empirical studies evaluating the implementation of these reforms at the local level remain limited. Recent reviews emphasized that while reforms were intended to promote inclusivity and entrepreneurship, inconsistencies in service delivery, bureaucratic inefficiencies, and weak capacity-building efforts at the municipal level have hindered their success (Sanabria-Pulido & Bello-Gómez, 2021; Serrano & Javate, 2023). Although national monitoring reports have pointed out issues such as ineffective communication, limited staff training, and underdeveloped sustainability initiatives (Development Academy of the Philippines, 2022; Memorandum Circular No. 12, Series of 2008), systematic analysis linking these operational dimensions to client satisfaction outcomes remains scarce, particularly in less urbanized areas such as Misamis Oriental.

The tangible dimensions of service quality—including office cleanliness, modern equipment, professional appearance of staff, and accessibility—play a critical role in shaping client perceptions and satisfaction, as affirmed by Brombacher, Houben, and Vos (2023), who concluded that tangible service elements build client trust and organizational legitimacy. However, many Negosyo Center's have not formally assessed how such tangible factors are associated with MSME engagement. Similarly, while employee competence, characterized by professionalism, technical skills, and responsiveness, has been widely recognized as crucial for public service effectiveness (Liu, Tang, & Chen, 2022), few local studies have empirically examined its association with client satisfaction within the context of Negosyo Center operations.

Moreover, with increasing attention to environmental responsibility, sustainable practices in public services are no longer optional but essential. The global shift toward green governance calls for agencies to minimize waste, optimize resource use, and integrate eco-friendly innovations into service delivery (UNEP, 2023). However, there is limited empirical work assessing how Negosyo Centers have adopted sustainable operational practices and whether such efforts affect client trust and loyalty. Recent studies highlight that integrating green practices into service delivery not only improves organizational image but also enhances customer satisfaction and loyalty (Huang et al., 2022; Najmaei & Sadeghinejad, 2022).

Addressing these gaps is vital to strengthening MSME participation, improving public sector efficiency, and fostering sustainable local economic development. By focusing on service quality, employee competence, and sustainable environmental practices, this study responds to emerging calls for evidence-based evaluations of local public service delivery reforms (Ruvalcaba-Gómez et al., 2023; Zafar et al., 2022).

By bridging these empirical gaps and aligning service improvements with key SDGs, this study offers timely insights into how Negosyo Centers can enhance service delivery, promote environmental responsibility, strengthen MSME engagement, and contribute to inclusive, sustainable economic development in the Philippines.

Research Questions

This study evaluated the association of the Negosyo Center service quality, employee competence and sustainable environmental practices in Salay, Misamis Oriental, on client satisfaction. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is clients' assessment of the service quality provided by the Negosyo Center in Misamis Oriental, in terms of:
 - 1.1 Tangibles
 - 1.2 Reliability
 - 1.3 Responsiveness
 - 1.4 Assurance
 - 1.5 Empathy
2. What is the clients' assessment of the Employee Competence of the Negosyo Center's employees in terms of:
 2. 1 skills, and
 2. 2 professionalism?
3. What is the clients' assessment of the sustainable environmental practices of the Negosyo Center?
4. What is the extent of client satisfaction among MSMEs with the services provided by the Negosyo Center in Misamis Oriental?
5. Are the clients' assessments of quality service, employee competence, and sustainable environmental practices significantly associated with their satisfaction in a negosyo center in Misamis Oriental?

METHODOLOGY

This research employed a quantitative type of study with a descriptive-correlational research design to establish the correlation between service quality, employee competence, sustainable environmental practices and client satisfaction of MSMEs in a Negosyo Center in Misamis Oriental. As Bhandari (2021) demonstrated, a descriptive-correlational research design allows for the identification of relationships between different factors, facilitating the recognition of patterns and trends that can predict future outcomes.

Participants and the Sampling Procedure

The research employed a sample of MSME clients who had directly benefited from the services provided by the Negosyo Center in Misamis Oriental. To ensure adequate data for analysis and enhance the reliability of the findings, a minimum of 104 participants was included after computing for the Taro Yamane formula. Random sampling was used to select those who were readily available and willing to provide feedback. Data were collected through two main methods: first, feedback forms were distributed immediately after service delivery, and second, online questionnaires were sent to clients who still needed to complete the on-the-spot feedback forms.

To validate the sample, participants were carefully selected based on the following criteria: 1.) The participant must be an owner or representative of a Micro, Small, or Medium Enterprise (MSME) in Misamis Oriental. 2.) The participant must have received services from the Negosyo Center within 5 months in 2025. 3.) The participant must be willing to share feedback about their experience with the services received.

Research Instrument

To achieve the study's objectives, the researcher utilized a structured questionnaire adapted from Devi, Lepcha, and Basnet (2023), focusing on service quality, employee competence, sustainable environmental practices and client satisfaction, contextualized for the Negosyo Center in Misamis Oriental. The instrument was organized into four key sections: The first section, Service Quality, assessed the tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy dimensions as outlined in the SERVQUAL model (Parasuraman et al., 1988; Cronin & Taylor, 1992; Devi et al., 2023). The second section evaluated Employee Competence, measuring the skills, professionalism, and problem-solving abilities of staff members assisting MSME clients (Mirchuk, 2023; Grant, 1996; Barney, 1991; Vieira, 2005), to determine how employee capabilities are connected to service delivery and client satisfaction (Zeithaml et al., 1996; Parasuraman et al., 1985). The third section focused on Sustainable Environmental Practices, examining the Negosyo Center's initiatives on environmental sustainability and their association with client satisfaction (Samitthiwetcharong et al., 2023; Esthi et al., 2023; Rassiah et al., 2024; Macheca et al., 2024; Chen et al., 2023). Finally, the Client Satisfaction section evaluated whether services met or exceeded client expectations, integrating measures of service quality, staff efficiency, and overall client experience (Bitner, 1990; Morgan & Hunt, 1994; Ricardianto et al., 2023; Laksana & Ekawati, 2020). Collectively, these components provided a comprehensive framework for analyzing the factors influencing client satisfaction at the Negosyo Center.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1. What is the clients' assessment of the service quality provided by the Negosyo Center in Misamis Oriental, in terms of: 1.1 tangibles, 1.2 reliability, 1.3 responsiveness, 1.4 assurance, and 1.5 empathy?

Table 1
Summary Table of Service Quality

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
<i>Tangibility</i>	4.95	Very High	0.13
<i>Reliability</i>	4.93	Very High	0.16
<i>Responsiveness</i>	4.94	Very High	0.15
<i>Assurance</i>	4.93	Very High	0.15
<i>Empathy</i>	4.94	Very High	0.14
Service Quality	4.94	Very High	0.12

Table 1 presents that the Negosyo Center’s overall service quality received a very high rating (Mean = 4.94, SD = 0.12), demonstrating a strong level of client satisfaction with the services rendered. Each aspect of service quality received a very high rating, highlighting the center's steadfast commitment to improving service delivery.

The data further showed that clients greatly valued the clean and professional environment of the office, as reflected in the high Tangibility score of 4.95. The well-maintained space helped build trust and confidence in the services provided, resulting in a better and more positive experience (Parasuraman et al., 1988). This aligned with Özdemir-Güzel and Baş (2020), who emphasized that the physical environment shapes customer perceptions, satisfaction, and loyalty in service settings. The Reliability score of 4.93 also indicated that clients saw the office as reliable, consistently delivering accurate and effective services that strengthened their trust and encouraged long-term engagement (Zeithaml et al., 1990). Grönroos (1984) also noted that reliable service delivery is a critical factor for customer retention. Additionally, the Responsiveness score of 4.94 indicated that clients felt the staff had been very attentive to their needs, offering timely assistance and ensuring their satisfaction (Kalia et al., 2021). This is further supported by Singh and sharma (2023), who emphasized that prompt service is essential to customer satisfaction and overall experience. Furthermore, this level of attentiveness helped establish a strong sense of Assurance, with a score of 4.93, as clients had confidence in the staff’s expertise and clear communication, knowing they were in capable hands Gunawardana and Gamlath (2024). According to Musheke and Phiri (2021), professional staff behavior and clear communication contribute to service assurance and client trust.

Research Question 2. What is the clients’ assessment of the Employee Competence of the Negosyo Center employees in terms of skills and professionalism?

The results in the summary table show that the overall employee competence at the Negosyo Center was rated Very High, with a mean score of 4.95 and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.10. This means that most participants strongly agreed that the employees were highly competent as also indicated in the homogeneity of their responses. Mengesha (2021) emphasized that employee competence is vital for attracting and retaining customers and eventually to customer satisfaction.

Table 2
Summary Table of Employee Competence

<i>Dimensions</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>SD</i>
<i>Skills</i>	4.95	<i>Very High</i>	0.12
<i>Professionalism</i>	4.96	<i>Very High</i>	0.12
<i>Employee Competence</i>	4.95	<i>Very High</i>	0.10

Among the two areas measured, Professionalism had the highest rating (mean = 4.96, SD = 0.12). This implies that clients appreciated the employees' politeness, honesty, and respectful behavior. Skills also had a Very High rating ($M = 4.95$, $SD = 0.12$), which meant that employees were seen as knowledgeable and able to help with business concerns effectively. Damayanti et al. (2021) stressed that employee professionalism is crucial to customer satisfaction. Their study indicated that well-trained and professional employees developed trust and loyalty, while high-quality service enhanced the overall client experience. Furthermore, professionalism in service delivery encourages customer engagement, which leads to client satisfaction and improved business performance. This was also supported by Montano et al. (2024), who emphasized the significance of professionalism in shaping client experiences, particularly in service-oriented environments.

Research Question 3. What is the clients' assessment of the Sustainable Environmental Practices of the Negosyo Center?

Table 3 depicts the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of the participant's assessment of sustainable environmental practices in a Negosyo Center within a Local Government Unit (LGU). This table reflects an overall mean score of 4.73, which indicates that most participants strongly agreed that the Negosyo Center adopted sustainable environmental practices. A large majority, 68.27% of participants rated these practices as always practiced, while 31.73% rated them as often practiced, demonstrating that nearly all clients recognized the office's eco-friendly initiatives. The standard deviation (SD) of 0.32 signals that participants had different views, but showed a strong agreement on the sustainability efforts of the Negosyo Center. These findings aligned with Rassiah et al. (2024), who emphasized that businesses should integrate eco-friendly strategies into their operations to reduce environmental footprint and support long-term sustainability.

Table 3

Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Participant's Assessment of Sustainable Environmental Practices

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	<i>Always Practiced</i>	71	68.27
3.51-4.50	<i>Often Practiced</i>	33	31.73
2.51-3.50	<i>Sometimes Practiced</i>	0	0
1.51-2.50	<i>Rarely Practiced</i>	0	0
1.00-1.50	<i>Not Practiced at All</i>	0	0
Total		104	100.0
Overall Mean		4.73	
Interpretation		Always Practiced	
SD		0.32	

Research Question 4. What is the extent of client satisfaction among MSMEs with the services provided by the Negosyo Center in Misamis Oriental?

Table 4 indicated that overall client satisfaction with the services provided by the Negosyo Center was exceptionally high, with an overall mean score of 4.91 and a standard deviation of 0.21. Out of 104 participants, 96 (92.31%) rated their satisfaction as "Very High," while 8 (7.69%) rated it as "High." This finding highlights that clients had a very positive perception of the services they received. The findings showed that the Negosyo Center delivered services that met clients' expectations, leading to high satisfaction levels. Supriyanto et al. (2021) supported this, stating that clients were generally more satisfied when services were reliable and their expectations were effectively met by the employees.

The results indicated that the Negosyo Center provided effective, prompt, and easily accessible services, leading to high levels of client satisfaction. The consistently very high ratings across all areas emphasized how much clients valued the staff's professionalism, the ease of accessing services, and the clear communication they received. These findings were in line with previous research on client satisfaction, which emphasized the importance of maintaining excellent service quality to ensure positive client experiences (Rahman, Mukhlis, Murwani, & Said, 2023). As a result, these insights could help the Negosyo Center refine its services to meet customer needs and expectations further.

Table 4

Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Participant's Assessment of Client Satisfaction

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	96	92.31
3.51-4.50	High	8	7.69
2.51-3.50	Moderate	0	0
1.51-2.50	Low	0	0
1.00-1.50	Very Low	0	0
Total		104	100.0
Overall Mean			4.91
Interpretation			Very High
SD			0.21

Research Question 5. Do the clients' assessments of quality service, employee competence, and sustainable environmental practices have a significant association with their satisfaction in a Negosyo center in Misamis Oriental?

Ho1: There is no significant association between service quality dimensions and client satisfaction.

Ho2: There is no significant association between employee competence and client satisfaction.

Ho3: There is no significant association between sustainable environment practices and client satisfaction.

Table 5 present the Spearman-Rho correlation analysis of the service quality dimensions on client satisfaction reveals significant positive relationships across all dimensions. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected, implying that the participants who assessed the service quality of the Negosyo center highly were also more satisfied.

Looking at the result, Tangibility ($r = 0.515$), though slightly lower in correlation, still played an important role in client satisfaction. This referred to the physical environment of the Negosyo Center, including the cleanliness, organization, and availability of modern equipment. A well-maintained and professional-looking space created a positive impression and enhanced client confidence in the services offered. Zeithaml et al. (2020) found that a clean and organized business environment significantly associated to customer perceptions of service quality. In the workplace, a well-maintained and organized office space not only created a good first impression when clients entered but also helped them feel safe and comfortable with the services provided.

Moreover, the results showed that service reliability ($r = 0.600$) and responsiveness ($r = 0.571$) were key factors associated with client satisfaction. A strong correlation showed

that clients greatly valued both the consistency and efficiency of the services provided. Reliability, which reflected the Negosyo Center's ability to meet commitments and fulfill expectations, reassured clients that they could depend on the center for their business needs. When services were delivered as promised, clients felt more confident and satisfied.

At the same time, responsiveness measured how quickly and effectively the staff addressed concerns, answered questions and offered assistance. The positive correlation revealed that clients felt valued and prioritized when staff responded quickly and efficiently. In any office environment, prompt and efficient responses from employees make the client experience more positive, while delays could lead to frustration and complaints.

These findings supported the work of Parasuraman et al. (1988), who showed that reliability and responsiveness were key factors in customer satisfaction, as they built trust and provided a smooth service experience. Going beyond the standard services not only boosted client satisfaction but also strengthened the office's credibility and commitment to delivering quality. Furthermore, the results stressed the importance of continuous improvement in reliability and responsiveness to maintain high service standards and ensure smooth, hassle-free transactions. By being dependable and responsive, the Negosyo Center was able to build strong relationships with its clients.

Assurance, which refers to the confidence and security clients feel when interacting with the Negosyo Center staff, also plays a major role. The findings underscored how different aspects of service quality contributed to enhancing client satisfaction. Among these factors, assurance had the highest correlation with client satisfaction ($r = 0.778$), highlighting its crucial role in shaping the overall experience of entrepreneurs and clients using the center's services.

Additionally, empathy ($r = 0.464$) was positively correlated with client satisfaction. Empathy reflected staff members' ability to understand and address clients' unique needs. Entrepreneurs often faced challenges that required personalized support, and when staff demonstrated empathy, it strengthened relationships and enhanced overall satisfaction. Jain, S., & Sundström, M. (2021) emphasized that empathetic service was essential for building long-term customer relationships. The results showed that empathy made clients feel heard and understood, which led to higher satisfaction and loyalty. When staff were able to connect with clients' concerns, it made them more likely to keep using the services.

Table 5

Spearman Rho Correlation result of the association between the Participant's Assessment of Service Quality on Client Satisfaction

		<i>Tangibi</i>	<i>Reliabi</i>	<i>Responsive</i>	<i>Assurance</i>	<i>Empa</i>	<i>Service</i>
		<i>lity</i>	<i>lity</i>	<i>ness</i>		<i>thy</i>	<i>Quality</i>
<i>Client</i>	<i>Correlat</i>	<i>.515**</i>	<i>.600**</i>	<i>.571**</i>	<i>.778**</i>	<i>.464**</i>	<i>.657**</i>
<i>Satisfacti</i>	<i>ion</i>						
<i>on</i>	<i>Coeffici</i>						
	<i>ent</i>						
	<i>Sig. (2-</i>	<i>.000</i>	<i>.000</i>	<i>.000</i>	<i>.000</i>	<i>.000</i>	<i>.000</i>
	<i>tailed)</i>						

Significant at 0.05 level

Table 6 present the Spearman-Rho correlation analysis of employee competence and on client satisfaction.

Among the three variables, employee competence had the strongest correlation ($r = .666$), emphasizing the key role of skilled and professional staff in improving client experiences. This confirms that while all variables are positively related to satisfaction, employee competence showed the strongest association, making it a critical factor in service improvement. Therefore, the Ho2 null hypothesis is rejected. This means that employee competence and its dimension of skills and professionalism have significant association on client satisfaction.

The very high ratings in table suggested that clients strongly trust the staff's competence and dependability, which aligned with studies that emphasized the critical role of trust and reliability in creating positive customer experiences in government and business service environments (Bitner, 2020). In a similar vein, Beyari (2020) stated that trust plays a crucial role in service sectors, as individuals often turn to experts for guidance when making important decisions. When clients see that service providers are knowledgeable and dependable, their confidence in the organization increases, leading to higher satisfaction and loyalty. In today's business environment, providing consistent and good service helps retain clients for the long term and makes them more likely to recommend the Office to others.

Table 6

Spearman Rho Correlation result of the association between the Participant's Assessment of Employee Competence on Client Satisfaction

		<i>Employee Skills</i>	<i>Professionalism</i>	<i>Employee Competence</i>
<i>Client Satisfaction</i>	<i>Correlation Coefficient</i>	.662**	.596**	.666**
	<i>Sig. (2-tailed)</i>	.000	.000	.000

Significant at 0.05 level

Specifically, skilled employees ($r = 0.662$) were recognized as a critical element in ensuring a positive experience for clients. This emphasized the importance of having well-trained and knowledgeable staff, as their expertise played a crucial role in building trust and ensuring satisfaction with the services provided. At the Negosyo Center, staff guided entrepreneurs by providing accurate business advice, helping them navigate challenges, and connecting them with the right resources.

Clients who interacted with skilled and competent employees felt more supported and confident in their decisions, leading to higher satisfaction levels. These results aligned with Srinivasan (2024), who found that continuous employee training improved service quality, communication, and overall customer experience. Similarly, Zeithaml et al. (2020) emphasized that knowledgeable employees were essential in service-based industries, where clients relied on expert guidance to make informed decisions.

On the other hand, professionalism ($r = 0.596$) was also positively correlated with client satisfaction. Professionalism involved how staff members presented themselves, communicated, and handled client interactions. When employees presented themselves with professionalism, it builds trust and developed a sense of security, making clients feel respected and valued (Bitner, 2020).

The combination of strong skills and professionalism greatly contributed to client satisfaction in any business support office. Employees with knowledge were able to meet clients' needs and provide helpful solutions. Professionalism, such as respectful communication, good behavior, and consistency, helped build trust. Investing in training and maintaining a professional environment strengthened client relationships. Overall, skilled and professional employees not only improved the client experience but also enhanced the office's reputation and trustworthiness.

Table 7 presents the Spearman Rho Correlation analysis between sustainable environmental practices on client satisfaction. Sustainable environmental practices had a moderate association with client satisfaction ($r = 0.517$).

Table 7

Spearman Rho Correlation result of the association between the Participant's Assessment of Sustainable Environmental Practices on Client Satisfaction

		<i>Sustainable Environmental Practices</i>
<i>Client Satisfaction</i>	<i>Correlation Coefficient</i>	<i>.517**</i>
	<i>Sig.(2-tailed)</i>	<i>.000</i>

Significant at 0.05 level

Clients appreciated the Negosyo Center's sustainability initiatives, such as reducing waste, using eco-friendly materials, and promoting responsible business practices. Thus Ho3 null hypothesis is rejected. This means that sustainable environmental practices have bearing in client satisfaction.

The awareness of environmental issues grew, people became more inclined to support organizations that aligned with their values. Khan et al. (2020) also stated that adopting sustainable practices was associated consumer choices, especially in service industries where environmental responsibility has become increasingly important.

To enhance its sustainability efforts, the Negosyo Center could have planned initiatives that focused on eco-friendly practices and created sustainability-driven programs. This would have strengthened its connection with clients who valued environmental responsibility. Additionally, promoting these efforts through marketing and communication could further help the center raise awareness and attract more clients who prioritise sustainability.

Overall, the results showed that service quality, employee competence, and sustainability were crucial factors driving client satisfaction at the Negosyo Center. Among the various elements of service quality, assurance stood out as the most significant, indicating a high level of trust in the services offered. However, empathy received the lowest score, though still in a very high range, pointing to the potential for further strengthening customer relationships.

On the other hand, employee competence, particularly in terms of skills, played a pivotal role in ensuring exceptional service delivery, emphasizing the importance of well-trained personnel. Sustainability demonstrated potential for growth, presenting opportunities for long-term advancements. Although the ratings were already high, focusing on areas like tangibles, empathy, responsiveness, and sustainability could still improve service delivery, and focusing on other areas that needed to be addressed could create a more supportive environment for entrepreneurs and local businesses.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the study provided a comprehensive understanding of how service quality, employee competence, and sustainable environmental practices were associated with client satisfaction among MSME clients of the Negosyo Center in Misamis. The findings confirmed key aspects of the SERVQUAL model (Parasuraman et al., 1988), demonstrating that assurance, reliability, and responsiveness were critical factors Shaping clients' perceptions of service quality. In addition, the results affirmed the Satisfaction Theory, which posits that client satisfaction arises when services meet or exceed expectations, particularly through the delivery of competent and professional service. Although sustainable environmental practices showed a positive association with client satisfaction, they were not as highly prioritized by the center, indicating a valuable opportunity for future improvement.

The consistently high ratings reflected not only the performance of the Negosyo Center but also the broader achievements of the local government unit, which has earned recognition for governance and innovation at the national level. Awards such as the Husay Negosyo Center-DTI Region 10 Buwalan Award, the 2023 "Most Responsive Negosyo Center" recognition, and the LGU's multiple Seal of Good Local Governance honors likely strengthened clients' favorable perceptions. Nevertheless, the study emphasized the need for ongoing improvements, especially in enhancing sustainability initiatives and addressing resource limitations, to further advance MSME development and contribute to sustained local economic growth.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are offered:

1. The local government units may allocate funds from their annual budget, particularly under economic development programs, to support the center's operations, training, and MSME initiatives.
2. The Negosyo Center manager may collaborate with local businesses or cooperatives to secure funding for additional services, enhancing its capacity to support MSMEs.
3. The office manager providing business support
 - 3.1 may create a simple and accessible way for MSMEs to share their feedback. Frequent reviews can help identify areas for improvement to ensure that services adhere to meet the shifting expectations of clients in terms of the business environment.
 - 3.2 Adapt and refine its feedback instrument to truly reflect the needs of its clients. Clients should have the option to provide feedback either face-to-face with printed forms available at the office, or through online forms and email. This flexibility ensures that the feedback process is hassle-free, allowing clients to choose the most convenient method for sharing their thoughts on the services provided.
4. Future Researchers may explore studies on the association between entrepreneur satisfaction and factors such as business environment, available support, entrepreneurial skills, and technological accessibility.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to the Belmont Principles to ensure the ethical and fair treatment of all participants throughout the research process. The principle of respect for persons was applied by allowing participants to make an informed, voluntary decision to participate, after being fully apprised of their rights, including their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any form of penalty or negative consequence. No incentives were provided, maintaining the voluntariness of their participation and avoiding undue influence, as emphasized in recent interpretations of ethical guidelines for human research (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2018; Resnik, 2020).

The principle of beneficence was likewise upheld by prioritizing participants' well-being, minimizing potential risks, and ensuring that the anticipated benefits of the study outweighed any possible harm. This approach is consistent with updated ethical research frameworks that stress researchers' obligations to protect participants from harm and to enhance possible benefits (Faden, Beauchamp, & Kass, 2014). Privacy and confidentiality were strictly maintained by assigning code numbers to each response and limiting access to data solely to the researcher.

Justice was demonstrated by employing fair selection procedures to ensure that no group was unjustly excluded or disproportionately burdened. This was aligned with ethical standards that require equitable distribution of research burdens and benefits among diverse populations (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2018).

Before data collection began, the researcher submitted the complete research protocol to the Lourdes College Research Ethics Committee for review and approval. This process ensured compliance with national and institutional ethical standards, including the Data Privacy Act of 2012 of the Philippines, which protects individuals' personal information used in research contexts. Upon approval, informed consent was systematically secured from each participant. Personal data were handled with strict confidentiality; access was restricted to authorized personnel only, and data security measures, including password protection and encryption, were implemented in accordance with best practices for safeguarding digital information (Buchanan & Zimmer, 2019).

After data collection, participant responses were systematically coded, organized, and securely stored. Data were retained only for a limited period necessary for research purposes and were subsequently destroyed through secure deletion or physical shredding. Participants were informed about the data retention and destruction processes, and in case of any security or privacy concerns, immediate corrective action would be undertaken to protect participants' rights and data integrity.

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